

POSTBUCKLING ANALYSIS OF LAMINATES BASED ON A MIXED VARIATIONAL FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

A variational formulation in terms of the transverse deflection $w(x,y)$ and the in-plane stress function $F(x,y)$ is used to obtain postbuckling solutions of plates. The appropriate variational functional is obtained naturally from the potential energy functional by means of the partial Legendre transformation. Boundary conditions involving in-plane displacements come out as natural boundary conditions for the stress function, and are satisfied in an averaged sense by virtue of the extremization process. Using the present formulation, Rayleigh-Ritz solutions are obtained for the axisymmetric postbuckling problem of a clamped circular plate. Superior accuracy and convergence trends are found when compared with similar solutions based on a purely displacement formulation. The results have significant implications on the analysis of delaminations in a composite laminate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional analytical and numerical solutions of large deflection and postbuckling deformation of homogeneous and laminated plates are based on a purely displacement formulation involving the middle-surface displacements, $u(x,y)$, $v(x,y)$ and $w(x,y)$. In such solutions, the in-plane forces and bending and twisting moments, which determine the stresses in the plate, are obtained from the membrane strains and the curvatures of the deformed middle surface. Solution of large deflection problems of plates by nonlinear finite-element analysis is exceedingly laborious, especially if a large number of degrees of freedom must be used to obtain reasonably accurate results for the stresses. A less costly approximate solution procedure, such as the Rayleigh-Ritz method, is attractive from a practical point of view.

In the Rayleigh-Ritz method, the solution of the plate problem is represented by a linear combination of admissible functions which individually satisfy the geometrical boundary conditions. The unknown coefficients of the representation are determined by extremizing the variational functional with respect to the admissible argument functions. If the number of coefficients is not sufficiently large, the analysis results for the stress and moment resultants are generally poor, and the convergence of solutions is slow, even though the results for the transverse deflection may be highly accurate. This observation has been emphasized in a detailed and thorough analysis and convergence study of the postbuckling solutions of circular plates by the Rayleigh-Ritz method (Yin & Jane, 1992), where the series solutions with increasing polynomial orders were examined and compared with the solution obtained by direct integration of the von Karman equations (Yin, 1985).

The results suggest that the stresses in the plate as determined by many existing large-deflection or postbuckling solutions are liable to very significant errors, despite the demonstrated accuracy of these solutions in predicting the transverse deflection. For anisotropic elliptical and rectangular laminates, Rayleigh-Ritz solutions that can provide reasonably accurate results for the stresses and their resultants may require several scores of expansion coefficients (see Feng, 1983 and Jane & Yin, 1992, respectively, for the results concerning rectangular and elliptical laminates).

An alternative to the displacement formulation is the use of a mixed formulation in terms of the transverse deflection $w(x,y)$ and the in-plane stress function $F(x,y)$. Numerical solutions using the mixed formulation generally provide better results for the in-plane forces. However, if the in-plane displacements are specified over a portion of the boundary, then the integration of the coupled system of differential equations for the functions w and F may be complicated by very elaborate boundary conditions for the stress function. In practice, the use of the mixed formulation in nonlinear analysis of plates has been largely restricted to the case where the *entire* boundary of the plate is subjected to specified or vanishing in-plane forces (see, for example, Chia, 1980).

The mixed formulation was used by Rhodes and Harvey (1971) and, more recently, by Kunz (1989) to obtain postbuckling solutions of plates with more general types of boundary conditions. In these works the boundary conditions of the displacement type or of the mixed type were treated by an elaborate integration scheme to yield certain relations which were subsequently imposed on the coefficients of the series expansion.

In this paper, we propose an alternative approach, which circumvents the difficulty of the mixed formulation (associated with the displacement boundary conditions on the stress function) by using the variational method. A generalized variational functional Ω is obtained naturally from the total potential energy functional by means of the partial Legendre transformation, which involves the change of the argument functions from u , v and w to w and F . Boundary conditions for the in-plane displacements become natural boundary conditions for the stress function. They are satisfied automatically, in an averaged sense, by virtue of the solution process.

The present method is illustrated with application to axisymmetric postbuckling deformation of a thin, isotropic circular plate subjected to a inward radial displacement along its boundary. Polynomial expansions of various degrees for the functions $w(r)$ and $F(r)$ are used and substituted into the functional Ω . As the number of coefficients in the polynomial expansions increases, the Rayleigh-Ritz solutions of the present method converge rapidly and become almost indistinguishable from the solution obtained by direct integration (Yin, 1985). Compared to the Rayleigh-Ritz solutions using a purely displacement formulation, the solutions of the present method (using the same total number of expansion coefficients) yield membrane forces and radial moments with remarkably improved accuracy.

2. THE VARIATIONAL FUNCTIONAL Ω

Let $u_\alpha(x,y)$ ($\alpha = 1, 2$) denote the in-plane displacements of the middle surface of a homogeneous or laminated anisotropic plate and let $w(x,y)$ be the transverse deflection. According to von Karman's theory, the strain-displacement relations in moderately large deflection of the plate are given by

$$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 - z w_{,\alpha\beta} = (u_{\alpha,\beta} + u_{\beta,\alpha} + w_{,\alpha} w_{,\beta})/2 - z w_{,\alpha\beta} \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0$ denotes the membrane strain tensor and the commas indicate partial differentiation with respect to the in-plane coordinates. We assume that the bending-stretching coupling stiffness

vanishes for the laminate, so that the strain energy may be partitioned into separate parts associated with stretching and bending (this is the case if a composite laminate has a symmetric lay-up with respect to the middle plane). Then the elastic constitutive equations for the stress and moment resultants $N_{\alpha\beta}$ and $M_{\alpha\beta}$ are:

$$N_{\alpha\beta} = A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^{\circ}, \quad M_{\alpha\beta} = D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} w,_{\gamma\delta}, \quad (2)$$

The stiffness matrices $A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ and $D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ satisfy certain symmetry conditions, i.e., $A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = A_{\gamma\delta\alpha\beta} = A_{\beta\alpha\gamma\delta} = A_{\alpha\beta\delta\gamma}$ and identical relations for $D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$. In the absence of tangential surface loads, the stress resultants $N_{\alpha\beta}$ satisfy the equilibrium equations $N_{\alpha\beta, \beta} = 0$. This implies the existence of a stress function $F(x,y)$ such that

$$N_{\alpha\beta} = e_{\alpha\gamma} e_{\beta\delta} F,_{\gamma\delta}, \quad (3)$$

where $e_{11} = e_{22} = 0$ and $e_{12} = -e_{21} = 1$.

Consider the following boundary conditions for the laminate:

$$u_{\alpha} = u_{\alpha}^{\circ}(x,y) \text{ along } \partial B_u; \quad N_{\alpha\beta} n_{\beta} = T_{\alpha}^{\circ}(x,y) \text{ along } \partial B_{\sigma} \quad (\alpha = 1,2) \quad (4a,b)$$

where $\partial B_u \cup \partial B_{\sigma} = \partial B$ is the boundary curve of the simply connected region B occupied by the plate, n_{α} is the unit outward normal vector on ∂B , and u_{α}° , T_{α}° are specified boundary data. These boundary conditions must be supplemented by additional conditions for w , $\partial w/\partial n$ or their conjugate kinetic variables (edge shear force and edge moment). Equation (3) and the identity $e_{\beta\delta} n_{\beta} = s_{\delta}$ imply that the second boundary condition of Eq. (4) is equivalent to the following:

$$s_{\beta} F,_{\alpha\beta} = e_{\beta\alpha} T_{\beta}^{\circ}. \quad (5)$$

where s_{δ} denotes the unit tangent vector on ∂B . If the plate is subjected to a distributed transverse load $q(x,y)$, then the total potential energy of the present problem is given by

$$\Pi = U_m + U_b - \iint q(x,y) w(x,y) dx dy - \int_{\partial B_{\sigma}} u_{\alpha} T_{\alpha}^{\circ} ds \quad (6)$$

where

$$U_m = (1/2) \iint A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\circ} \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^{\circ} dx dy, \quad (7a)$$

$$U_b = (1/2) \iint D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} w,_{\alpha\beta} w,_{\gamma\delta} dx dy. \quad (7b)$$

Now define V_m^* , a functional depending on $N_{\alpha\beta}$ and $w,_{\alpha\beta}$, by the partial Legendre transformation of U_m involving the change of the argument functions from $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\circ}$ and $w,_{\alpha\beta}$ into $N_{\alpha\beta}$ and $w,_{\alpha\beta}$:

$$\begin{aligned} V_m^* &= -U_m + \iint N_{\alpha\beta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{\circ} dx dy = -U_m + \iint N_{\alpha\beta} (u_{\alpha, \beta} + w,_{\alpha} w,_{\beta} / 2) dx dy \\ &= -U_m + \iint (1/2) N_{\alpha\beta} w,_{\alpha} w,_{\beta} dx dy + \oint u_{\alpha} N_{\alpha\beta} n_{\beta} ds \end{aligned}$$

Replacing U_m on the right hand side of Eq. (6) by V_m^* , we obtain a new functional

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &= V_m^* + U_b - \iint q(x,y) w(x,y) dx dy - \int_{\partial B_{\sigma}} u_{\alpha} T_{\alpha}^{\circ} ds \\ &= - (1/2) \iint Q_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} F,_{\alpha\beta} F,_{\gamma\delta} dx dy + \iint \{ (1/2) D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} w,_{\alpha\beta} w,_{\gamma\delta} - q w \} dx dy \\ &\quad + \iint (1/2) e_{\alpha\gamma} e_{\beta\delta} F,_{\gamma\delta} w,_{\alpha} w,_{\beta} dx dy + \int_{\partial B_u} u_{\alpha}^{\circ} e_{\alpha\gamma} e_{\beta\delta} F,_{\gamma\delta} n_{\beta} ds, \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$Q_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = e_{\alpha\kappa} e_{\beta\lambda} e_{\gamma\mu} e_{\delta\nu} (A^{-1})_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}. \quad (9)$$

Solutions of the laminated plate are determined by the variational equation $\delta\Omega = 0$. By first restricting the admissible variations δw and δF to the special class which vanish along the entire boundary, we obtain the Euler-Lagrange equations

$$Q_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} F_{,\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} + w_{,xx} w_{,yy} - (w_{,xy})^2 = 0, \quad (10a)$$

$$D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} w_{,\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} - F_{,yy} w_{,xx} - F_{,xx} w_{,yy} + 2 F_{,xy} w_{,xy} - q(x,y) = 0. \quad (10b)$$

Natural boundary conditions are obtained from the line integrals of the variational equation when the additional restrictions on the admissible δw and δF are removed.

3. POSTBUCKLING SOLUTIONS OF A CLAMPED CIRCULAR PLATE

We consider the axisymmetric postbuckling deformation of an *isotropic* circular plate subjected to the following displacement boundary conditions at $r = a$:

$$w = 0, \quad w' = 0, \quad u_r = -\epsilon_0 a \quad (11)$$

where w and u_r depend only on the radial coordinate r . Continuity of the slope at the center of the plate requires that w' also vanishes at $r = 0$. The stress function $F(r)$ determines the radial and circumferential membrane forces according to the following expressions:

$$N_r = F'(r)/r, \quad N_\theta = F''(r). \quad (12)$$

One may set $F(0) = 0$ because an additive constant in the stress function does not affect the stress components. The transverse load $q(x,y)$ is assumed to be absent. Substitution of the preceding equations into Eq. (8) yields the following expression for the functional Ω

$$\Omega = \pi \int_0^a \left[\frac{1}{Eh} \{ r (F'')^2 + (F')^2/r - 2 \nu F' F'' \} - D r (w'' + w'/r)^2 - (w')^2 F' \right] dr - 2\pi a \epsilon_0 F'(a). \quad (13)$$

where $D = Eh^3/\{12(1-\nu^2)\}$ is the bending rigidity, h is the thickness of the plate, E is the Young's modulus and ν is the Poisson's ratio. Consequently

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(\Omega/2\pi) = & \int f' \delta F dr - \int g' \delta w dr - f(a) \delta F(a) - g(0) \delta w(0) \\ & + (1/Eh) \{ a F''(a) - \nu F'(a) - Eh\epsilon_0 a \} \delta F'(a) + (\nu/Eh) F'(0) \delta F'(0). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The condition $\delta\Omega = 0$ yields the Euler-Lagrange equations $f' = g' = 0$, and the natural boundary conditions

$$f(a) = 0, \quad g(0) = 0, \quad F'(0) = 0, \quad F''(a) - (\nu/a) F'(a) = Eh \epsilon_0.$$

Integrating the Euler-Lagrange equations and making use of the first two natural boundary conditions, we obtain $f(r) \equiv g(r) \equiv 0$, or,

$$(r F'')' - F'/r + (Eh/2) (w')^2 = 0, \quad D \{ (r w'')' - w'/r \} - w' F' = 0. \quad (15)$$

Hence the postbuckling problem of a clamped circular plate under a radial displacement loading at the boundary is described by Eq. (15) and the following set of boundary conditions

$$w(a) = 0, \quad w'(0) = w'(a) = 0, \quad (16a,b,c)$$

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F'(0) = 0, \quad F''(a) - (v/a) F'(a) - Eh \epsilon_0 = 0. \quad (16d,e,f)$$

Since the last two boundary conditions for the stress function F are natural, they need not be, although they may be, imposed on the class of admissible stress functions in an approximate method of analysis. The extremizing procedure in the solution scheme will ensure satisfaction of these conditions in an averaged sense if they are not satisfied *a priori*.

Extending the work of Friedrichs and Stoker (1942) for simply-supported plates, Bodner (1954) presented differential equations and boundary conditions equivalent to Eqs. (15) and (16), and obtained solutions by the perturbation method. Solutions covering a considerably larger range of the strain load parameter ϵ_0 were obtained by Yin (1985), and were compared with the Rayleigh-Ritz solutions based on a displacement formulation (Yin and Jane, 1992).

Consider polynomial approximations of w and F of the form

$$\{24(1-\nu^2)\}^{-1/2} w(r)/h = (1-\xi^2)^2 (C_1 + C_3 \xi^2 + C_5 \xi^4 + C_7 \xi^6 + C_9 \xi^8), \quad (17a)$$

$$F(r)/D = C_2 \xi^2 + C_4 \xi^4 + C_6 \xi^6 + C_8 \xi^8 + C_{10} \xi^{10}, \quad (17b)$$

where ξ denotes the nondimensional radial coordinate, $\xi = r/a$. The preceding expressions satisfy all but the last natural boundary condition of Eq. (16). Substituting the expressions into $\delta\Omega = 0$ and varying the coefficients C_i independently, we obtain a system of nonlinear algebraic equations which may be solved iteratively for the undetermined coefficients. The condition $\delta\Omega = 0$ not only ensures the satisfaction of Euler-Lagrange equations in an average sense, it also ensures approximate satisfaction of the remaining natural boundary condition (Eq. (16f)) as well.

In order to investigate the accuracy and the convergence of Rayleigh-Ritz solutions, we compare five solutions of ascending order containing the first six, seven, eight, nine and ten undetermined coefficients in Eq. (17) for each given value of the strain load parameter ϵ_0 . The results for the central deflection, boundary radial force and the boundary bending moment are (i) compared among these five set of solutions, (ii) compared with the solution obtained by direct integration of the governing differential equations in conjunction with the shooting method (Yin, 1985) and (iii) compared with the Rayleigh-Ritz solutions based on polynomial expansions of comparable degrees for the radial and transverse displacements, u_r and w .

The two types of Rayleigh-Ritz solutions both yield accurate results for the central deflection (see Figs. 1 and 2). However, while the five solutions in the mixed formulation all yield boundary forces and moments that are in close agreement with the results obtained by direct integration (Figs. 3 and 5), the solutions based on the displacement formulation differ significantly in these results (Figs. 4 and 6). Displacement-based solutions containing a small number of undetermined solutions give especially poor predictions for the radial force along the boundary and in the interior of the plate. Although the Rayleigh-Ritz solutions using the mixed formulation do not satisfy the last natural boundary condition of Eq. (16) exactly, the error decreases rapidly and uniformly (over a wide range of the strain load parameter ϵ_0) as the number of undetermined coefficients in w and F increases. The error may be defined as the ratio of the computed value of the left hand side of Eq. (16f) to $Eh\epsilon_0$, and is shown in Fig. 7 for the five solutions based on the mixed formulation.

From a computational viewpoint, the accuracy of the lower-order Rayleigh-Ritz solutions in the present approach is very important. Refined Rayleigh-Ritz solutions, comparable in accuracy to those obtained here for the special case of axisymmetric postbuckling of a circular plate, may require tremendous computational effort in general two-dimensional problems of anisotropic rectangular or elliptical plates. Findings of the present study suggest that reasonably accurate solutions for the in-plane forces and moments may be obtained for general anisotropic elliptical laminates by using 24 undetermined coefficients in the (F, w) formulation, whereas solutions of comparable accuracy in the purely displacement formulation may require 85 undetermined coefficients because the lower-order polynomial expansions for the displacements yield poor results for the in-plane forces and the bending moments.

In the analysis of buckling-initiated delamination growth in composite laminates, accurate results for the boundary forces and moments in the various postbuckling states of a two-dimensional delaminated layer are required to assess the peeling and shearing action and the strain energy release rates at the delamination front. Furthermore, the solution process must be repeated at the various stages of delamination growth. Repeated use of three dimensional nonlinear finite element analysis is too time consuming and costly for the problem, while Rayleigh-Ritz solutions based on a pure displacement formulation and involving a moderately large number of coefficients do not yield sufficiently accurate results for the boundary forces and moments. The study of the present paper suggests that the Rayleigh-Ritz method based on the mixed formulation may be the right approach for investigating postbuckling deformation and growth behavior of a disbanded composite layer.

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References

- Bodner, S. R. (1954), "The postbuckling behavior of a clamped circular plate," *Quart. J. Appl. Math.*, Vol. 12, pp. 397-401 (1954).
- Chia, C.-Y. (1980), *Nonlinear Analysis of Plates*. McGraw Hill, New York.
- Feng, M. (1983), "An energy theory for postbuckling of composite plates under combined loading," *Computers & Structures*, Vol. 16, pp. 423-431.
- Friedrichs, K. O., and Stoker, J. J. (1942), "Buckling of the plate beyond the critical thrust," *ASME J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 9, pp. 7-14 (1942).
- Jane, K.C. and Yin, W.-L. (1992), "Refined buckling and postbuckling analysis of two-dimensional delaminations - II. Results for anisotropic laminates and conclusion," *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 29, pp. 611-639.
- Kunz, R. K. (1989), "Postbuckling of stiffened composite plates under combined loading," *Proc. 8th DOD/NASA/FAA Conference on Fibrous Composites in Struc. Design*, Norfolk, VA, Nov. 28-30.
- Rhodes, J. and Harvey, J. M. (1971), "The postbuckling behavior of thin flat plates in compression with the unloaded edges elastically restrained against rotation," *J. Mech. Engrg. Sci.*, Vol. 13, pp. 82-91.
- Washizu, K. (1982), *Variational Methods in Elasticity and Plasticity*, 3rd Ed. Pergamon Press, Oxford.
- Yin, W.-L., (1985) "Axisymmetric buckling and growth of a circular delamination in a compressed laminate," *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 21, pp. 503-514.
- Yin, W.-L. and Jane, K.C. (1992), "Refined buckling and postbuckling analysis of two-dimensional delaminations - I. Analysis and validation," *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 29, pp. 591-610.

$$M(1) = \frac{a^2 M_r}{hD} \text{ Mixed formulation}$$

Fig. 5: Boundary radial moment

$$M(1) = \frac{a^2 M_r}{hD} \text{ Displacement Formulation}$$

Fig. 6: Boundary radial moment

$$\text{ERR} \quad \text{Mixed formulation}$$

Fig. 7: Normalized error of Eq. (6b)

Figure legends

- Solution with 6 coefficients
- - - Solution with 7 coefficients
- Solution with 8 coefficients
- · - · - Solution with 9 coefficients
- - - - - Solution with 10 coefficients